

Angelo Leogrande^{1*°}

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

The Transition to University in the Italian Regions

Between 2013 and 2020 it grew on average by 5.22%

Istat calculates the value of the variable indicated as "Transition to University". The transition to university is defined as the percentage of recent high school graduates who enrol for the first time at university in the same year in which they obtained their upper secondary school diploma - cohort specific rate. Writings to Higher Technical Institutes, Institutes of Higher Artistic, Musical and Dance Education, Higher Schools for Linguistic Mediators and foreign universities are excluded. The data analysed refers to the period 2013-2020. The data relating to Trentino Alto Adige were omitted due to the presence of missing values in the historical series present in the original ISTAT-BES dataset.

Ranking of the regions by value of the transition to university in 2020. Umbria is in first place for the value of the transition to university in 2020 with a value of 61.1 units, followed by Molise with an amount of 59.5 and from Abruzzo with a value of 59.1. In the middle of the table are Lombardy with an amount of 55.7 units, and Emilia Romagna and Basilicata with a value of 55.6. Sicily closes the ranking with a value of 46.8 units, followed by Valle d'Aosta with an amount of 42.6, and Campania with 41.5.

Ranking of the regions by value of the percentage change in the transition to university between 2013 and 2020. Umbria is in first place for the value of the percentage change in the transition to university with an amount of 20.99% equal to an amount of 10.6 units, followed by Sicily with a value of 10.64% equal to an amount of 4.5 units and Puglia with a value of 9.76% equal to an amount of 4.5 units. In the middle of the table are Abruzzo with a value of 7.07% equal to an amount of 3.9 units, followed by Basilicata with an amount of 5.9% equal to an amount of 3.1 units and Molise with a value equal to 5.87% equal to an amount of 3.3 units. Calabria closes the ranking with a value of 1.6% equal to an amount of 0.8 units, followed by Campania with a value of -6.95% equal to an amount of -3.1 units and Valle d' Aosta with an amount of -19.01% equal to an amount of -10 units.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. The data highlights the presence of two different clusters:

- Cluster 1: Lombardy, Piedmont, Emilia Romagna, Lazio, Liguria, Marche, Abruzzo, Umbria, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Tuscany, Basilicata, Molise, Valle d'Aosta, Veneto, Calabria;
- Cluster 2: Sicily, Campania, Puglia, Sardinia.

We can see that cluster 1 is dominant compared to the value of cluster 2. The following ordering of the clusters is thus determined: $C1 > C2$. The regions of Cluster 1 are made up of Central-Northern regions with some notable exceptions, namely: Basilicata, Calabria, Abruzzo. The regions of Cluster 2 are instead made up of the majority of southern regions. The analysis therefore shows not so much

¹Assistant Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.culture@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

a contrast between the regions of the Centre-North and the southern regions, but rather the backwardness of some southern regions, namely Sicily, Campania, Puglia and Sardinia, is evident.

Italian Macro-Regions. The value of the transition to university grew in Northern Italy between 2013 and 2020 from an amount of 52.7 up to a value of 54.4 or a change equal to an amount of 1.7 units equivalent to a value of 3.23%. The value of the transition to university grew in the period between 2013 and 2020 from an amount of 51.8 units up to a value of 56.2 units or a variation equal to an amount of 8.49% equal to an amount of 4.4 units. The value of the transition to university in the South grew from an amount of 46 units up to a value of 47.2 units or a variation equal to an amount of 2.61% equal to an amount of 1.2 units. Overall in Italy the value of the transition to university grew from an amount of 49.7 units up to a value of 51.9 units or equal to an amount of 4.43% equal to an amount of 2.2 units.

Machine Learning and Predictions. Below is a predictive analysis with a comparison of eight machine learning algorithms. Machine learning algorithms are evaluated based on their ability to maximize the R-squared and minimize statistical errors, i.e.: “Mean Absolute Error”, “Mean Squared Error”, “Root Mean Squared Error”. The algorithms are trained with 70% of the available data while the remaining 30% is used for the actual prediction. Rankings are then created for each algorithm. The score that each algorithm obtains in each ranking is added into an overall ranking. The algorithm that has the lowest score is the most efficient in predictive terms. The following ordering of algorithms is then identified:

- Tree Ensemble Regression with a payoff value of 4;
- Linear Regression with a payoff value of 9;
- Random Forest Regression with a payoff value of 11;
- Simple Regression Tree with a payoff value of 16;
- PNN-Probabilistic Neural Network with a payoff value of 21;
- ANN-Artificial Neural Network with a payoff value of 25;
- Gradient Boosted Trees Regression with a payoff value of 26;
- Polynomial Regression with a payoff value of 32.

Therefore the most efficient algorithm in predictive terms is Tree Ensemble Regression. By applying the Tree Ensemble Regression algorithm it is possible to obtain the following predictions:

- Puglia with a negative prediction from an amount of 50.6 units up to a value of 47.81 units or a variation equal to an amount of -2.79 units equal to an amount of -5.51%;
- Marche with an increase from an amount of 57.8 units up to a value of 58.09 units or equal to an amount of 0.29 units equal to a value of 0.50%;
- Tuscany with a decreasing variation from an amount of 55.9 up to a value of 55.83 units or equal to an amount of -0.07 units equal to a value of -0.13%;
- Emilia Romagna with a decreasing variation from an amount of 55.6 units up to a value of 55.59 units or equal to a value of -0.01 units equal to a value of -0.02%;
- Veneto with an increasing variation from an amount of 52.7 units up to a value of 53.67 units or equal to a variation of 0.97 units equal to a value of 1.84%;
- Calabria with a decreasing variation from an amount of 50.9 units up to a value of 50.76 units or equal to a value of -0.14 units equal to a value of -0.28%.

On average, the value of the prediction for the indicated regions presents a decreasing variation from an amount of 53.9 units up to a value of 53.62 units or a variation of -0.29 units equal to a value of -0.54 %.

Conclusions. The value of the transition to university grew in the period considered, i.e. between 2013 and 2020, reaching a value of 55.68 on average in the Italian regions. That is, this value means that on average 55.68% of high school students enrol in university in the same year in which they obtain their diploma. Obviously, Italians who enrol in universities abroad are excluded. And furthermore, the variable also excludes students who also enrol in the Conservatory, the Academies of Fine Arts, the Higher Technical Institutes and the Schools of Linguistic Mediators. Therefore, the variable only considers students who enrol in universities and polytechnics. The values of the transition to University in the Italian regions highlight a contrast between the Central-Northern regions and the Southern regions. Although there are southern regions that have very positive performances in terms of transition to university such as Molise with 59.5% in 2020, Abruzzo with 59.1%, and Basilicata with 55.6% . In the last places are Puglia, Sardinia, Sicily, Campania and also Valle d'Aosta. The transition to university is very relevant in an economy that is increasingly oriented towards knowledge, especially technical-scientific knowledge. However, in the future of work, specialized technical figures such as engineers, physicists, mathematicians, chemists and computer scientists will not only be central, but professional figures expert in the human and social sciences will also be relevant. In fact, even in the abundance of technology that has been produced in connection with the fourth industrial revolution, one can feel within industries and institutions the lack of managerial leadership profiles that can guide work teams and give companies and public organizations a new vision and mission to successfully face the challenge of digital transformation. For these same reasons, I also feel like criticizing Istat's choice not to include people enrolled in Conservatories, Academies of Fine Arts, Higher Technical Institutes and Schools for Linguistic Mediators, from the variable "*Transition to University*". In fact, it is very likely that design, industrial techniques, and internationalization achieved through the growth of linguistic-cultural mediation professionals can help private companies and public organizations obtain those competitiveness and productivity advantages that are so lacking in the current "*Italian technocratic deluge*".

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Passaggio all'Università 2020		
Rank	Regioni	2020
1	Umbria	★ 61,1
2	Molise	★ 59,5
3	Abruzzo	★ 59,1
4	Liguria	★ 58,1
5	Marche	★ 57,8
6	Toscana	★ 55,9
7	Piemonte	★ 55,7
8	Lombardia	★ 55,7
9	Emilia-Romagna	★ 55,6
10	Basilicata	★ 55,6
11	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	★ 55,3
12	Lazio	★ 55,3
13	Veneto	★ 52,7
14	Calabria	★ 50,9
15	Puglia	★ 50,6
16	Sardegna	★ 50,1
17	Sicilia	★ 46,8
18	Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	★ 42,6
19	Campania	★ 41,5

Passaggio all'Università. Media delle Regioni Italiane tra il 2013 ed il 2020 con esclusione del Trentino Alto Adige. Fonte: Istat-BES.

Passaggio all'Università nelle Regioni Italiane tra il 2013 ed il 2020. Fonte: Istat-BES

Regioni	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Piemonte	★ 52,90	★ 51,70	★ 52,50	★ 52,40	★ 53,30	★ 52,90	★ 54,20	★ 55,70
Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	★ 52,60	★ 52,80	★ 49,10			★ 50,20	★ 50,00	★ 42,60
Liguria	★ 55,10	★ 53,80	★ 54,90	★ 55,20	★ 53,10	★ 55,40	★ 55,90	★ 58,10
Lombardia	★ 53,60	★ 52,60	★ 54,70	★ 54,40	★ 54,40	★ 54,50	★ 55,90	★ 55,70
Veneto	★ 50,50	★ 50,40	★ 51,10	★ 50,40	★ 50,40	★ 50,20	★ 50,50	★ 52,70
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	★ 51,30	★ 50,40	★ 52,80	★ 51,50	★ 52,40	★ 51,90	★ 53,80	★ 55,30
Emilia-Romagna	★ 53,20	★ 51,70	★ 52,90	★ 51,50	★ 53,00	★ 53,60	★ 54,90	★ 55,60
Toscana	★ 51,80	★ 50,10	★ 52,50	★ 52,50	★ 52,10	★ 51,90	★ 52,90	★ 55,90
Umbria	★ 50,50	★ 50,00	★ 52,40	★ 53,90	★ 54,30	★ 54,90	★ 57,40	★ 61,10
Marche	★ 53,10	★ 53,60	★ 54,90	★ 54,30	★ 55,40	★ 56,10	★ 57,50	★ 57,80
Lazio	★ 51,60	★ 51,10	★ 52,30	★ 53,10	★ 53,50	★ 53,80	★ 55,20	★ 55,30
Abruzzo	★ 55,20	★ 54,60	★ 54,80	★ 56,70	★ 56,60	★ 57,70	★ 58,00	★ 59,10
Molise	★ 56,20	★ 58,10	★ 56,20	★ 54,40	★ 57,10	★ 56,30	★ 53,90	★ 59,50
Campania	★ 44,60	★ 44,40	★ 45,10	★ 44,00	★ 43,10	★ 43,70	★ 43,00	★ 41,50
Puglia	★ 46,10	★ 47,20	★ 47,10	★ 47,50	★ 48,00	★ 48,30	★ 50,20	★ 50,60
Basilicata	★ 52,50	★ 52,70	★ 52,80	★ 51,50	★ 49,50	★ 52,50	★ 54,60	★ 55,60
Calabria	★ 50,10	★ 48,50	★ 49,80	★ 50,30	★ 50,40	★ 49,10	★ 50,00	★ 50,90
Sicilia	★ 42,30	★ 41,60	★ 42,60	★ 43,70	★ 44,50	★ 43,80	★ 46,60	★ 46,80
Sardegna	★ 46,10	★ 45,10	★ 47,60	★ 48,70	★ 48,30	★ 50,10	★ 50,80	★ 50,10
Media	★ 51,02	★ 50,55	★ 51,37	★ 51,44	★ 51,63	★ 51,94	★ 52,91	★ 53,68

Errori Statistici degli Algoritmi di Machine Learning per la Predizione del Valore Futuro del Passaggio all'Università

Algorithm	R ²	Mean absolute error	Mean squared error	Root mean squared error
ANN	★ 0,33641269	★ 0,20781027	★ 0,10824866	★ 0,32901164
PNN	★ 0,26596727	★ 0,19437212	★ 0,08692275	★ 0,29482664
Simple Regression Tree	★ 0,68317016	★ 0,14620270	★ 0,03879427	★ 0,19696260
Gradient Boosted Trees Regression	★ 0,05713082	★ 0,24884330	★ 0,10022029	★ 0,31657589
Random Forest Regression	★ 0,78062936	★ 0,09189129	★ 0,02287712	★ 0,15125185
Tree Ensemble Regression	★ 0,99066592	★ 0,02032048	★ 0,00100000	★ 0,03114115
Linear Regression	★ 0,85252379	★ 0,09892794	★ 0,01859329	★ 0,13635721
Polynomial Regression	★ -0,98259376	★ 0,37643678	★ 0,28591954	★ 0,53471445

Risultati delle Statistiche e Metrici delle Predizioni con gli Algoritmi di Machine Learning					
Algorithms	R ²	Mean absolute error	Mean squared error	Root mean squared error	Totale
Tree Ensemble Regression	★ 1	★ 1	★ 1	★ 1	★ 4
Linear Regression	★ 2	★ 3	★ 2	★ 2	★ 9
Random Forest Regression	★ 3	★ 2	★ 3	★ 3	★ 11
Simple Regression Tree	★ 4	★ 4	★ 4	★ 4	★ 16
PNN	☆ 6	☆ 5	☆ 5	☆ 5	★ 21
ANN	☆ 5	☆ 6	☆ 6	☆ 7	★ 25
Gradient Boosted Trees Regressi	☆ 7	☆ 7	☆ 7	☆ 6	★ 26
Polynomial Regression	☆ 8	☆ 8	☆ 8	☆ 8	★ 32

